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Further Strengthening the Role of the Oliy Majlis and Political Parties in the Conditions of Deepening Democratic Reforms in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the process of reform, issues related to improving parliamentary activities, which are among the priorities of the action strategy. The role of government bodies, in particular, the Parliament, in the organizational and legal support of reforms at a new stage of the country's development is emphasized.*

Key words: *parliament, strategy, reform, lawmaking, MP inquiry.*

INTRODUCTION AND RELEVANCE.

It is worth noting that the decree "The Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 7, 2017 priority is given to attached great importance to democratic reforms aimed at improving the construction of the state and society and strengthening the role of the parliament in the modernization of the country, improving the public administration system[1]. This historical document determined the directions of the country's development in the near future. Specifically, it states that "Reducing the state's participation in the economy to a strategic level, further developing private property, and solving complex issues related to its protection"[2] are the most important tasks for the government, state administration bodies, and hakimiyat at all levels. The "Action Plan" defines several directions and tasks for the modernization of state administration during this stage of the liberalization of society.

RESEARCH METHODS.

First, to implement the principles that determine the criteria of democratic state management into life steadily and rapidly. These are the priority of human rights and interests in management, distribution of powers (including rational distribution of powers between the bodies implementing state management), the rule of law, broad involvement of public and civil society institutions in state management, transparency and openness of the activities of state management bodies.

Secondly, it is envisaged to improve the legislative and legal framework of the state administration apparatus based on modern requirements.

Thirdly, the rationalization of the structure and functions of the bodies involved in management in the system of executive power is considered an important task of the administrative reform. In this case, it is necessary to eliminate the presence of parallel structures and duplication of each other's tasks in the state administration.

Fourthly, it is necessary to ensure the openness of the activities of state administration bodies, to create effective mechanisms that ensure their cooperation with civil society institutions, and to activate public control over their activities.

Fifthly, consistent improvement of the legal bases (regulations) of the activities of relevant competent bodies is especially important in the modernization of state administration and increasing the effectiveness of administrative reforms. Among such legal documents, the adoption of the Administrative Procedure Code, the Laws "On Administrative Procedures" and "On Public Service" are mentioned in the program.

RESEARCH RESULTS.

Public service is the performance of personnel functions of management by state bodies, the activities of persons who hold permanent or temporary positions in the apparatus of state bodies and are provided with funds from the state budget. The civil service is one of the main types of state activity in terms of organization and legal regulation of the management of the state apparatus, and ensures the effective implementation of the tasks before the state.

The main purpose of public service in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to fulfill the functions of the state, fulfill its duties, and serve the interests of society and citizens, based on the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In our opinion, in order to regulate the general aspects of public service, the law "On public service of the Republic of Uzbekistan" should include a chapter on public service, and the procedure for entering public service, attestation of public servants, their promotion, and responsibility of public servants should be determined in separate articles.

"We are seriously working on creating an effective system for training new independent thinking, responsible, initiative, advanced management methods, honest personnel loyal to their country and people. We will fight hard to completely eliminate cases of negligence and irresponsibility among civil servants when considering citizens' appeals. The people themselves will evaluate the performance of the leaders, based on the level of trust in them and the effective solution of the problems of the people. Therefore, in order to increase the responsibility of the employees of state institutions and also to strengthen the guarantees of their rights, we put forward the initiative of adopting the law "On Public Service" [3] – he said.

Qualification levels of civil servants indicate the level of professional training in accordance with the qualification requirements of the respective civil service positions. The granting of qualification levels to civil servants is determined depending on the compliance of the professional training level of civil servants with qualification requirements. Qualification levels are determined based on the results of state qualification exams or certification. The conduct of qualification examinations, the granting of qualification levels, and their storage in connection with their transfer to another job are determined by legal documents [4].

In our country, the procedure for awarding qualification levels or special titles to civil servants is determined by separate regulatory and legal documents. Also, in the legislature of our republic, career degrees are awarded in a consistent manner, if there is a positive attestation, higher education according to the qualification, taking into account the position and work experience, as well as special titles given in the previous work or place of service.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized the audience: "I think it's time to develop a purposeful program that includes the important issues of forming a practical reserve of personnel, training and retraining them to achieve the goals set before us. The main task is to form a new team of managers and officials who have high professional skills and modern thinking, who are well-thought-out, who can make the right decisions in all aspects, and who can achieve the set goals. In this regard, it is necessary to pay special attention to the training of qualified personnel for the territorial administration bodies, first of all, the district and city hokims of our country" [5].

Training of professional personnel and improvement of their qualifications will have a positive effect on the promotion of employees through the ranks of the service. For this purpose, personnel training is considered one of the important directions. Therefore, in many countries, together with centralized training, a comprehensive system of courses is used, which is important for the preparation of personnel reserves for the promotion of civil servants to higher positions and the professional development of managers.

CONCLUSION.

It is important to form a reserve of personnel to occupy leadership positions on the basis of competition in order to occupy the positions of the civil service in the order of growth in the state bodies. Thus, in the strategic program, it is emphasized that the improvement of the legislation on public service is of great importance for the proper and efficient operation of the public service. "Ensuring legitimacy in assessing the activities of state bodies and officials, how the rights and freedoms of citizens are protected, and the quality and openness of providing public services to them must be the main criteria for us. In this regard, I would like to repeat one more point: the people should not serve the state bodies, but the state bodies should serve our people" [6].

In general, as in all aspects of the social change society in Uzbekistan, the national parliament, the role of political parties in it, and the renewal of the public service system are demanding to be renewed. It is necessary to understand the nature of social-political, socio-political relations that are spreading in this country, and train personnel in accordance with modern requirements, in contrast to the old personnel, system.

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